

Gamified Teaching Strategies and English Proficiency of Grade 7 Students in Private Higher Education Institution

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Abstract:

The main thrust of this study was to determine the utilization level of gamified teaching strategies of English teachers and English Proficiency of Grade 7 students of Saint Francis of Assisi College Schools System. An online manual guide "OMG-GAME" Online Manual Guide for Gamified Activities for Motivation and Engagement was the output of the study. This descriptive-correlational study utilized the purposive sampling technique for the selection of the teachers' respondents and simple stratified random sampling technique for the selections of Grade 7 students' respondents. It included eight SFAC schools with 31 English Teachers and 112 students. A validated survey questionnaire was utilized with the Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test of .973 and .986 along with standardized questionnaire for gathering the data needed. A four-point Likert Scale for the gamified teaching strategies, a five-point Likert Scale for the English Proficiency level, and Pearson Coefficient (Pearson's r) were utilized resulting in the collected findings of the study. Findings showed that the utilization level of gamified teaching strategies of English teachers in terms of motivation, discussion, assessment, and application was Fully Utilized while assessment of English teachers and Grade 7 students concerning gamified-teaching strategies further revealed that there was a significant relationship between the two groups of respondents. On the other hand, the findings also showed that the English Proficiency level of Grade 7 students in terms of listening and reading revealed that majority of the students can attain proficient level meanwhile in terms of speaking and writing, majority of the students belong to the beginning level. Lastly, there was significant relationship between the utilization level of gamified teaching strategies in terms of motivation and discussion and the English Proficiency level among the English teachers and Grade 7 students in Saint Francis of Assisi College School System (SFAC).

Keywords: gamified teaching strategies, English proficiency, Grade 7 students, English teachers

Introduction

An essential component of a thriving modern society is English proficiency. English language is deemed as "global language," or the "lingua franca of the modern era.". The ability to understand English will empower him or her to succeed. English may be regarded as a global language given that it is the language that most people in practically every region of the world can speak and comprehend. However, it has been discovered that English proficiency is falling in the Philippines (EF, 2017). Additionally, Senator Sherwin Gatchalian (Philippine News Agency, 2022) stated that the Philippines ranked last in reading in the same international assessment in which 79 countries took part, with only one out of five Filipino students meeting the required proficiency level. Moreover, Malinowski (2021), Tomlison (2017), and Igbokwe, (2020) mentioned different problems that the students encountered in their writing and reading skills therefore the authors recommend that teachers must use variety of methods in teaching English Language. prove their skills in writing, reading, speaking, and listening while enjoying the lesson.

In learning contexts, students are required to read, write, speak, and comprehend English. Teaching English involves providing tactics designed to pique students' attention and eventually assist them advance their knowledge and proficiency in the language, similarly to any other teaching-learning process. New teaching techniques that increase students' motivation and commitment while maximizing their knowledge acquisition have been developed in this pandemic-era context. Gamification is one technique that has drawn the attention of educators, who have been investigating its potential to enhance student learning over the past few years. (Majuri et al., 2018; Koivisto and Hamari, 2019).

Gamification has become prevalent in learning environments more frequently to boost student engagement and promote social interaction. As a result, games have been used in an array of educational settings at various levels of education, demonstrating their ability to enhance learning results (Koivisto & Hamari, 2019). It seems that several studies of Nahmod (2017), El Tantawi, Sadaf and AlHumaid (2018), Bal (2019), Hariadi et al. (2021), Ahmed (2021) and Zhu et al. (2018) showed the consistent with the findings of the previous studies which stressed that the use of gamification was effective in improving students' writing, listening, speaking, and reading skills.

Mee Mee et al. (2020), Alberti (2021) and Kaya and Sagnak (2021) stated that utilization of gamification in classroom strengthen its place in education over the years and it is frequently preferred in teaching English. In addition, Tu et al. (2019), Ketola (2019), Prathyusha (2020), and Al-Dosakee and Ozdamli (2021) believed that the main purpose of implementing gamification concept in teaching was to engage and motivate learners in English Language. The researcher of the current study agreed with the statement of the authors mentioned. It is significant nowadays to utilize gamified teaching strategies especially for the 21st century learners who easily get bored in the discussion.

Hence, it could be argued that through improving students' timely comprehension and consequently facilitating more effective learning, gamified teaching strategies have a significant positive impact on the process of teaching English. This phenomenon inspired the proponent of the current study to investigate alternative strategies for inspiring learners who get demotivated because of the pandemic while enhancing their level of English proficiency. Hence, it is, therefore, the intention of the researcher to understand and to determine the correlation utilization level of gamified teaching strategies and English proficiency level of the Grade 7 students in Saint Francis of Assisi College.

Methods

This study utilized the quantitative research method particularly the descriptive-correlational research design. The instrument used in measuring the utilization of gamification is a validated self-made questionnaire with reliability level between .973 and .986. Meanwhile, the researcher used a standardized exam from liveworksheet.com in measuring the students' English Proficiency. The study was conducted among randomly selected 31 teachers and 112 respondents from a total of 294 Grade 7 students from the eight campuses of Saint Francis of Assisi College based on the analysis of a G*Power.

Results

Table 1.1 Utilization Level of Gamified Teaching Strategies as Assessed by English Teachers and Grade 7 Students in SFAC in terms of Motivation

Indicators in terms of Motivation During English Class, the teacher utilized gamified teaching strategies in MOTIVATION to:	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. arouse interest among students in the lesson	3.7 7	FU	3.5 0	FU	3.6 4	FU
2. direct students' attention to the activity	3.4 8	FU	3.5 0	FU	3.4 9	FU
3. develop a learning mindset among the students	3.5 8	FU	3.6 2	FU	3.6 0	FU
4. engage students in the learning process	3.6 8	FU	3.6 0	FU	3.6 4	FU
5. promote cooperative learning among students	3.6 5	FU	3.4 3	FU	3.5 4	FU
6. familiarize the students in the lesson	3.7 1	FU	3.6 8	FU	3.6 9	FU
7. provide fun interactivity that sustains enthusiasm in English class	3.7 1	FU	3.6 9	FU	3.7 0	FU
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.6 5	FU	3.5 7	FU	3.6 1	FU

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 1.75 – 2.49 Partially Utilized (PU)
2.50 – 3.24 Utilized (U) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

The utilization level of gamified teaching strategies as assessed by English Teachers and Grade 7 students in SFAC in terms of Motivation had a general assessment of 3.61 verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized as seen in Table 1.1. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized. The result implies that motivation towards the students and their teachers is fully utilized towards the betterment of the two parties. The result of this part of the study mirrors the way teachers and students make use of technology to make classroom interaction more fun and enjoyable has contributed to the students' motivation levels (Anisa, et al., 2020; Buljan, 2021)

Table 1.2 Utilization Level of Gamified Teaching Strategies as Assessed by English Teachers and Grade 7 Students in SFAC in terms of Discussion

Indicators in terms of Discussion During English Class, the teacher utilized gamified teaching strategies in Discussion to:	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. expand topic awareness for the teaching-learning activities	3.52	FU	3.70	FU	3.61	FU
2. enhance interactive engagement	3.77	FU	3.55	FU	3.66	FU
3. improve students' communication skills	3.45	FU	3.57	FU	3.51	FU
4. emerge students' previous knowledge to present knowledge	3.55	FU	3.60	FU	3.57	FU

5. ripen students' willingness to participate in the learning process	3.58	FU	3.56	FU	3.57	FU
6. make learning informative and exciting	3.71	FU	3.63	FU	3.67	FU
7. develop confidence in communication	3.61	FU	3.52	FU	3.57	FU
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.60	FU	3.59	FU	3.59	FU

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 1.75 – 2.49 Partially Utilized (PU)
2.50 – 3.24 Utilized (U) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

The utilization level of gamified teaching strategies as assessed by English Teachers and Grade 7 students in SFAC in terms of Discussion had a general assessment of 3.59 which was verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized as seen in Table 1.2. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized. This information posited that if teachers maintain the use of technology and/or game-based instruments in their classroom discussions, their students were expected to develop their cognition especially towards language and technology (Prodigy, 2019). Thus, this shows that teachers should also pay attention to less organized aspects of a lesson, such as decorating a classroom to complement the atmosphere of a lesson or assigning students with odd assignments (Blankman, 2022).

Table 1.3 Utilization Level of Gamified Teaching Strategies as Assessed by English Teachers and Grade 7 Students in SFAC in terms of Assessment

Indicators in terms of Assessment During English Class, the teacher utilized gamified teaching strategies in Assessment to:	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. allow assessment of students learning	3.61	FU	3.5 3	FU	3.57	FU
2. enhance comprehensive students' performance	3.65	FU	3.5 4	FU	3.60	FU
3. allow performance-based assessment	3.58	FU	3.5 4	FU	3.56	FU
4. develop participative assessment	3.81	FU	3.5 7	FU	3.69	FU
5. expand collaborative assessment	3.77	FU	3.5 2	FU	3.60	FU
6. offer challenges that spur student to greater achievement	3.58	FU	3.5 2	FU	3.55	FU
7. develop teamwork and good sportsmanship among students	3.77	FU	3.5 2	FU	3.65	FU
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.68	FU	3.5 2	FU	3.60	FU

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 1.75 – 2.49 Partially Utilized (PU)
2.50 – 3.24 Utilized (U) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

The utilization level of gamified teaching strategies as assessed by English Teachers and Grade 7 students in SFAC in terms of Assessment had a general assessment of 3.60 verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized as seen in Table 1.3. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized. The result shows that the use of gamification in the same way that it is used for the motivation of teachers and students as well as in the conversations that take place in the classroom leads to the same consequences for the assessment. According to Leonard (2022), teachers can provide students with several opportunities to apply what they had learned in context through gamifying courses as well as assessments early on in their educational journey.

Table 1.4 Utilization Level of Gamified Teaching Strategies as Assessed by English Teachers and Grade 7 Students in SFAC in terms of Application

Indicators in terms of Application During English Class, the teacher utilized gamified teaching strategies in Application to:	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. allow students to actualize what they learn	3.52	FU	3.56	FU	3.54	FU
2. develop integrative skills among the students	3.55	FU	3.53	FU	3.54	FU
3. develop outcome-oriented attitude among the students	3.61	FU	3.50	FU	3.56	FU
4. develop creative skills among the students	3.58	FU	3.63	FU	3.61	FU

5. progress interactive skills among students	3.68	FU	3.60	FU	3.64	FU
6. discover different ways to present what they learned	3.58	FU	3.56	FU	3.57	FU
7. promote storage of new information into long-term memory	3.58	FU	3.59	FU	3.59	FU
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.59	FU	3.57	FU	3.58	FU

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 1.75 – 2.49 Partially Utilized (PU)
2.50 – 3.24 Utilized (U) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized. It is evident that there is a full utilization of the gamified teaching strategies for the English class since the respondents gave a favorable response with regards to the strategies and the progress of the target students through compelling experiences (Feedier, 2022) and emphasis of the value of motivation (Anisa et al, 2020). The use of gamification helped learners become more engaged and prepared to assume responsibility for their own education. It was considered that lessons that included enjoyable activities were more effective in delivering a favorable outcome. According Mee et al. (2020) coined that utilizing gamification in the classroom would spark learners' interest and curiosity right away, resulting in their eagerness to study. A creative learning environment might be difficult to plan, though.

Table 2 Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the English Teachers and Grade 7 Students on the Utilization Level of Gamified Teaching Strategies

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F Ratio	Remarks	Decision
Motivation	Between Groups	.164	1	.164	.598	.44 1	Not Significant
	Within Groups	38.704	141	.274			
	Total	38.868	142				
Discussion	Between Groups	.002	1	.002	.007	.93 4	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.782	141	.254			
	Total	35.784	142				
Assessment	Between Groups	.648	1	.648	2.65	.10 5	Not Significant
	Within Groups	34.405	141	.244			
	Total	35.053	142				
Application	Between Groups	.008	1	.008	.039	.84 3	Not Significant
	Within Groups	29.628	141	.210			
	Total	29.636	142				

Level of significance 0.05

There was no significant difference between the responses of the English teachers and Grade 7 students on the utilization level of gamified teaching strategies as shown in Table 2. The generated computed probability values of Motivation, Discussion, Assessment, and Application were .441, .934, .105, and .843 respectively which were greater than the level of significance of 0.05; thus, accepting the null hypothesis.

This simply implies that the level of utilization of gamification in classrooms is fully utilized from the perspective of both students and teachers. According to Zainuddin (2020), it was feasible to monitor and evaluate a learner's progress while they were participating in gamification.

Table 3.1 English Proficiency Level of the Grade 7 Students in terms of Listening

Mean Score	Indicators	F	%
25.00 – 30.00	Advanced	9	8.04%
19.00 – 24.00	Proficient	28	25%
13.00 – 18.00	Approaching Proficient	27	24.11%
7.00 – 12.00	Developing	26	23.21%
0.00 – 6.00	Beginning	22	20%
Total		112	100%

For the listening proficiency of the Grade 7 students, 25% or 28 out of 112 were able to attain the proficient level meanwhile there were still 20% or 22 out of the 112 students in the beginning level on the 30-items Listening Examination as shown in Table 3.1.

The result reveals that most of the students fall into the proficient level, which could be considered as a gratifying result. However, there are still students who fall into beginner level, which makes it necessary for teachers to familiarize themselves with gamification to help students enhance their listening skills (de-Marcos et al., 2017). Thus, if teachers acquired an empirical understanding of the utilization gamification, they could help students in the beginning level to elevate their skills in listening.

Table 3.2 English Proficiency Level of the Grade 7 Students in terms of Speaking

Mean Score	Indicators	F	%
25.00 – 30.00	Advanced	2	1.78%
19.00 – 24.00	Proficient	3	2.68%
13.00 – 18.00	Approaching Proficient	19	16.96%
7.00 – 12.00	Developing	26	23.21%
0.00 – 6.00	Beginning	62	55.36%
Total		112	100%

Among the 112 respondents, 55.36% or 62 of them belonged to the beginning level meanwhile only 1.78% or 2 out of 112 Grade 7 students got advanced level on the 30-items Speaking Examination as seen from Table 3.2. The result shows that despite the use of gamification to enhance the English-speaking proficiency of the students, there are still more who need extra attention to elevate their conditions and become a part of those who are at least approaching proficiency. According to researchers (Abugohar et al., 2019; Nurlahim et al., 2019; Hidayati & Diana, 2019), Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) was more efficient in teaching speaking skills to students due to other factors that contributed to speaking such as confidence, independence, and flexibility. However, because gamification had been shown to be successful at motivating students, teachers may incorporate gamification components in non-digital ways with MALL to improve students' speaking skills. Furthermore, voluminous learning competencies were removed as part of DepEd's implementation of MELCs (Most Essential Learning Competencies). As a result, learning competencies related to speaking skills were also removed (Hernando-Malipot, 2020 that could have led the low performance of students in speaking.

Table 3.3 English Proficiency Level of the Grade 7 Students in terms of Reading

Mean Score	Indicators	F	%
25.00 – 30.00	Advanced	4	3.57%
19.00 – 24.00	Proficient	48	42.86%
13.00 – 18.00	Approaching Proficient	33	29.46%
7.00 – 12.00	Developing	19	16.96%
0.00 – 6.00	Beginning	8	7.14%
Total		112	100%

The data showed that 42.86% or 48 out of 112 Grade 7 students garnered a proficient level on the 30-items Reading Examination. The same result showed that 7.14% or 8 out of 112 Grade 7 students belong to the beginning level as seen in Table 3.3. The result reveals that most of the students garnered a proficient result for the reading test. However, there are still few students who belong to the beginning level, which means that the teacher should spend more time with them in English discussion and evaluations. Gamified education can assist beginners to develop their skills in the classroom. Therefore, with constant and effective use of gamification as well as progressive discussion in relation to reading, these students will eventually improve their reading skills (Desnenko et al., 2020).

Table 3.4 English Proficiency Level of the Grade 7 Students in terms of Writing

Mean Score	Indicators	F	%
25.00 – 30.00	Advanced	16	14.29%
19.00 – 24.00	Proficient	17	15.18%

13.00 – 18.00	Approaching Proficient	20	17.86%
7.00 – 12.00	Developing	17	15.18%
0.00 – 6.00	Beginning	42	37.50%
Total		112	100%

For the students' proficiency level in writing, 37.50% or 42 out of 112 belonged to the beginning level on 30-items Writing Examination. In addition, 14.29% or 16 out of 112 Grade 7 students were able to attain an advanced level as shown in Table 3.4. It implies that in the writing test a huge part of the population belongs to the beginning level. This is an alarming result considering that writing is one of the basic literacy skills that people must have. Similar to the situation of the students' speaking skills, the writing skills were not given enough attention due to the implementation of MELCs. Furthermore, gamification can only assist students up to the extent of mastering literary devices and writing conventions; it cannot, however, help them improve their writing skills in a subjective manner. However, because gamification has been proven to enhance student motivation (Saud, 2022; Bal 2019), teachers who utilize it as a motivational exercise for students when introducing a writing-related topic may encourage them to write more.

Table 4 Test of Significant Relationship between the Utilization Level of Gamified Teaching Strategies and English Proficiency Level of the Students

Utilization level of Gamified Teaching Strategies	English Proficiency Level	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Motivation	Listening	.212**	.025	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Speaking	.195*	.039	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Reading	.054	.573	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
Discussion	Writing	.216*	.022	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Listening	.203*	.032	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Speaking	.190*	.044	Significant	Reject H ₀
Assessment	Reading	.002	.985	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Writing	.099	.300	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Listening	.025	.791	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
Application	Speaking	.039	.685	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Reading	.019	.840	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Writing	.002	.987	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Listening	.008	.930	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Speaking	.036	.709	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Reading	.072	.449	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Writing	.054	.573	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

There was a significant relationship between the utilization level of gamified teaching strategies specifically Motivation and English Proficiency level specifically Listening, Speaking, and Writing as seen in the p-values of .025, .039 and .022., which were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, rejecting the null hypothesis as shown in Table 4. On the other hand, the computed probability value of Motivation and Reading was .573 that was greater than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, accepting the null hypothesis.

It can be concluded that gamification may not have a big impact on their reading abilities considering that reading is the primary focus of the curriculum's learning competencies most students are already adept reader. Thus, gamification could have less significant relationship with their reading skills, especially that learning competencies in the curriculum were focused mostly on reading.

Also, there was a significant relationship between the utilization level of gamified teaching strategies specifically Discussion and English Proficiency level specifically Listening and Speaking as seen in the p-values of .032 and .044., which were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. Conversely, the computed probability value of Discussion and Reading and Writing were .985 and .300 which were greater than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, accepting the null hypothesis. It implies that there are variety of outcomes related to the relationship between gamified teaching strategies specifically in discussion and English proficiency level in terms of listening, speaking, reading, and writing, including the individual differences of the students that may include their gender, game experience, learning style, player type, and personality trait (Dole, 2017; Barata, 2017). Based on the study of Landers and Armstrong (2017), benefits of gamification may vary according to some individual differences such as gender and game experience.

In addition, there was no significant relationship between the utilization level of Gamified teaching strategies in terms of Assessment and Application and the English Proficiency level in terms of Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing as seen in the p-values of .791, .685, .840, .987, .930, .709, .449 and .573 which were greater than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, accepting the null hypothesis. It implies that there are no links found between utilization of gamified teaching strategies specifically in assessment as well as in application and the English proficiency level of the students because they must finish their work independently during assessment and application the teachers may not realize that it is essential to maintain student's attention in class.

Conclusion

Based on the abovementioned findings of the study, the following conclusions have been obtained:

1. That English teachers of SFAC fully utilize gamification in their classrooms. It is evident that teachers utilize gamification in motivational activities, discussion, assessment, application. Since gamification may serve as a launching pad for their technologically enhanced career and lifestyle in the future, the researcher thought that this is a beneficial idea in current time when learning environments are shifting from one environment to another.
2. That the level of utilization of gamified teaching strategies in SFAC is fully utilized in the perspective of both students and teachers. This demonstrated that the educational system in the country improves the amount of knowledge that students learn because of modernization and technological advancement. Since the current generation of learners is more tech-inclined than the previous generation, gamified teaching practices are a great fit for them.
3. That the English proficiency level of the Grade 7 students particularly in speaking and writing test a huge part of the population belongs to the beginning level. Given that speaking and writing are two of the fundamental literacy abilities that every student should possess this result is concerning. Various factors that may have affected this such as the learning prioritized in MELCs as part of the implementation of distance learning during the COVID-19. Other contributing factors could also be the appropriateness of gamification tools provided in the curriculum maps with the target learning competency.
4. That the relationship between gamified teaching strategies and English proficiency in terms listening, speaking, reading, writing have varied results such as the individual differences of the students that might include their gender, game experience, learning style, player type, and personality trait. Furthermore, the need for motivation and attention may also vary from different learning activity; Thus, the link between gamification and English proficiency also varied in terms of target macro skill (listening, speaking, reading, writing).
5. That the Proposed Online Manual Guide is a helpful resource for the utilization of gamified teaching strategies of English teachers and English Proficiency of the Grade 7 students in Saint Francis of Assisi College.

Recommendations

Based on the outlined findings and finalized conclusions, the following recommendations are highly encouraged:

1. English teachers may take part in trainings and workshops that will advance their understanding of gamification and how to use it appropriately to improve the students' speaking, listening, reading, and writing abilities. Additionally, teachers may participate in trainings and workshops that shall help them utilize gamification tools during motivational activities, discussion, assessment, and application as well as discerning the need of gamification in instruction. Although gamification is proven to motivate students, teachers knowing the efficient timing of its use would make it more interesting for the students. Enriching the technological and pedagogical knowledge of the teachers could increase the chances of gamification to be more effective in their classes.
2. School administrators may arrange training and workshops that shall provide teachers with the knowledge they need to utilize gamification in a more efficient manner in their classrooms. Through this, teachers will find it easier to equip their selves with the right tools, greatest resources, and best practices in helping students improve their English proficiency. The said training may also be partnered with an Instructional Manual that teachers can use as a reference when they are planning their lessons. Through having a standardized manual, teachers will find it simpler and easier to integrate the use of gamification in their instruction.
3. School administrators, such as the principals, academic supervisors, and subject coordinators, may add learning competencies that prioritize the speaking and writing skills of the student's despite of it not being in the current curriculum. Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) is more effective at teaching speaking skills to students, that is why educational leaders, and teachers are urged to investigate their applications and ways to incorporate them into the teaching and learning process. Since speaking and writing are utilized often throughout all subject areas, they are crucial to a learner's development. Through focusing more on enhancing these skills, students could leverage their knowledge and skills in general.

4. Since there are no links found between gamification and assessment as well as in application, Developmental Research may be conducted to further determine if gamification is truly not beneficial in such context. Assessment and application are both strong objective indicators of learning outcomes. Subsequently, it might be beneficial if students are motivated will participating in those types of learning activities. Thus, a platform or a framework that shall cater to this may expound the impact of gamification in language learning.
5. Gamification is believed to be more beneficial when executed in a more intentional and strategic manner. Thus, the SFAC administrators may arrange workshops and trainings to guide teachers on how to use the best gamification tools of today as well as how to integrate it in teaching English as a Second Language among Filipino learners.
6. Future researchers may include the individual difference of learners such as gender, game experience, learning style, player type, and personality trait and explore their moderating and/or mediating role in the relationship of gamification and English proficiency. Furthermore, future researchers may also investigate the effect of gamification on English proficiency to determine other areas of gamification that shall be considered as to enhance the technological and pedagogical knowledge of English teachers.

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